

ACCIDENT PREVENTION USING V2V COMMUNICATION

GANESAN M¹, CHANDRALEKHA B², CHARULATHA R³

¹ASST.PROFESSOR, ^{2,3}UG SCHOLAR, RMK ENGINEERING

Email:char14121.ee@rmkec.ac.in

Abstract

Many accidents in road often occur when the other vehicle comes closer or near to the another vehicle and also travelling with high speed and cross each other on the road. Even the drivers are not aware of the vehicles while they come closer and they even forget to watch the mirror at times. This paper uses a zigbee network and ultrasonic sensors in order alert the drivers of the nearing vehicles on all the four side as to avoid the accidents. In spite of this prevention we have also used GSM and GPS to send information to a programmed number and the location if the accident is occurred.

Keywords: Vehicle system, alert, GPS, GSM, sensors, arduino

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the statistical report of National Institute of Disaster Management, there occurs a road accident over 80 per sec accounting to 1080 accidents in a day [2]. Accidents mostly occur when vehicles cross each other in a short gap and also the vehicles come close together in traffic on all sides. Hence the vehicles coming close to his vehicle from all the four sides and the drivers of corresponding approach vehicles which helps in avoiding accidents.

Authors of [3] developed a collision avoidance system if the front vehicles using laser scanning and collision prediction algorithm using the Kamm's circle.

Authors of [8] developed a system to locate the front vehicles using GPS (Global Positioning System) to locate and evaluate the relative velocity for finding a solution to avoid the collisions with the front vehicles.

Authors of [5] proposed a system that has external infrastructure that maintains the network of all vehicles in the coverage area and inform about the vehicle in a situation that may lead to collision. Then necessary action is taken to avoid collision. This system avoids vehicle to vehicle communication. In this method, systems that are enabled with Wi-Fi receive the

surrounding cars information and ZigBee is used to receive infrastructure information that will mitigate collisions.

Authors of [6] deployed fuzzy logy based controllers to develop and implement Collision Warning System (CWS) and Collision Avoidance System (CAS).

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed collision avoidance system consists of two parts.

- The main vehicle system
- The other vehicle system

The main vehicle system is installed in the vehicle whose security, in terms of collision avoidance, is the primary objective. The other vehicle system is installed in the approach vehicles that try to come close to the main vehicle within 2 meters range from all the sides. In practice both the systems are installed in every vehicle. The main vehicle system, installed in the main vehicle, senses the approach of any other vehicle from any of the four sides with the help of ultrasonic sound sensors and sends the corresponding activation signal to the other vehicle system installed in the surrounding vehicles that come close to the main vehicle within 2 meters. Then alert messages are displayed on the LCD of the vehicle approach warning system and also a buzzer is activated. Then the approach vehicle, in which the alert is activated, shall drive away from the main vehicle. Thus accidents can be avoided. The communication between the two sub-systems is established using ZigBee communication. The proposed system is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Proposed Collision Avoidance System vehicle

This system is built around the Atmega 328 microcontroller. Four ultrasonic sound sensors are attached to the car on all four sides. These sensors sense the vehicle approaching the main vehicle from any side sends an alert message to driver through liquid crystal display. The Main vehicle system communicates with the other vehicle through ZigBee communication. The block diagram of the VASS is shown in Fig. 2.

FIG 1. MAIN VEHICLE SYSTEM

FIG 2.OTHER VEHICLE SYSTEM

III. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

1.Hardware Implementation

The main components are sensors, Arduino, GSM, GPS, Zigbee Buzzer, LCD. Power is supplied to all the components by means of battery. Arduino is programmed in such a way when the approach vehicle comes closer it displays messages in LCD depending upon the position of the vehicle. If the vehicle met with an accident then the message is sent to the relations using GSM with the location using GPS.Buzzer is used in other vehicle system to alert the driver in order to maintain the distance between the vehicles.

Fig 3. MAIN VEHICLE SYSTEM

FIG 4. OTHER VEHICLE SYSTEM

2.Software Implementation

The software implementation is done by means of Arduino software. Programming of Arduino and interfacing of sensors with Arduino are the main part of software implementation. The programming part is done by using C language. The hardware circuit gets initialized as soon as the power supply is given to it. LCD display is interfaced with Arduino so that it displays the alert messages. The flowchart in fig 5 and fig 6 explains the working of lcd and buzzer in main vehicle system and other vehicle system. The main vehicle will send the signal to the zigbee transmitter and the other vehicle will receive the information through the zigbee receiver which will alert the buzzer.

Fig 5.Flowchart for main vehicle system

Fig 6. flowchart for other vehicle system

3.COMPONENTS USED

A.Ultrasonic sound sensor

An Ultrasonic sensor is a device that can measure the distance to an object by using sound waves. It will measure the distance by sending a sound wave at a specific frequency and listening for that sound wave that gets reflected back. By recording the time between the sound wave being generated and the sound wave that bounces back, it is possible to calculate the distance between the sonar sensor and the object. Four ultrasonic sensors is mounted on four sides of the vehicle. If the approaching vehicle enters within the two meters range of the main vehicle, the ultrasonic sound transmitted gets reflected and received by the receiver part of the ultrasonic sensor and it is converted into a electrical signal.

Fig 7. Interfacing arduino with ultrasonic sensor

B.Power supply

The block diagram of the power supply is shown in the in fig 1.It is a Full wave bridge rectifier with capacitor filter followed by a 3 pin 5V regulator (LM7805). From this 5V, using an LM1117 regulator, 3.3VDC is obtained. The 3.3V is used for the working of the Arduino and 5V for the rest of the circuit.

C.LCD display

A 16X2 LCD display, JHD 162A,DB0 TO DB3 is interfaced to the Arduino at D4 TO D7 in 4-bit mode to display the alert messages. When approach vehicle comes within 2 meters of distance, it displays “LEFT ALERT, RIGHT ALERT, FRONT ALERT and/or BACK ALERT” messages depending upon the position of the approach vehicle with respect to the main vehicle.

Fig 8. Interfacing arduino with lcd

D.GSM module

The GSM module (TXD) AND (RXD) is interfaced to the UART0 of the Arduino at pin2 and pin3 through RS232 interface using MAX232 IC.

SIM900 GSM Module interfacing to ARDUINO module

E.GPS MODULE

A GPS navigational device is any device that receives GPS signals and processes them to extract information for determining its exact location. Presented here is such a GPS device with a tracking record system. It shows the path traversed by driver from the initial position. Connect GPS module to Arduino UNO as following

- Vcc to 5v
- GND to GND
- RX to 9
- TX to 10

F.ZIGBEE MODULE

The ZigBee/802.15.4 module is interfaced to the UART1 of Arduino at (TXD) and (RXD). It operates at 2.4 GHz. The main vehicle communicates other vehicle through this module. It is a low power, low cost, and low data rate network and highly reliable means of wireless communication. It can establish its own network.

XBee Coordinator

Fig 9.interfacing arduino with zigbee module

G.BUZZER

Buzzer is used in other vehicle system to alert the driver not to hit the main vehicle and to maintain the correct distance between the two vehicles. Buzzer has two pins GND and Vcc. These are connected to the Vcc and GND of Arduino.

H.ARDUINO

The **Arduino Uno R3** is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328 . It has 14 digital input and output pins where 6 pins can be used as PWM outputs, 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It consists everything that needed to support the microcontroller. Simply connect it to a computer with a USB cable or power it with a AC-to-DC adapter or a battery to get started.

IV. RESULTS

The main vehicle system will be alerted when the approaching vehicle is nearing ,which will prevent from road accident. The GPS will sense the location of the vehicle and sends the message to a programmed number when the vehicle met with an accident. This shows the display of messages when the approach vehicle is not near the main vehicle and Fig. 11, Fig. 12, Fig. 13 and Fig 14, the messages when the approach vehicle approaches the main vehicle in different directions.

Fig 10.When No Approach Vehicle is in the Vicinity of Main Vehicle

Fig 11.Alert Message on LCD when Approach Vehicle is Left to the Main Vehicle

Fig 12.Alert Message on LCD when Approach Vehicle is Right to the Main Vehicle

V. CONCLUSION

The collision avoidance system using the main vehicle and other vehicle has been thoroughly tested and found working satisfactorily. This system used with every vehicle will warn the drivers so that they maintain minimum distance with other vehicles and can avoid collisions and accidents that aids in safe travel.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] . Dhanya K R and Mrs R Jeyanthi , “Advanced automatic braking system with sensor fusion concept”, International Journal of Emerging trends in Engineering and Development, ISSN 2249-6149, Issue 2, Volume 3 (April 2012).
- [2] Kedareswar, P.S. and Krishnamoorthy, V. A CAN protocol based embedded system to avoid rear-end collision of vehicles. IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Informatics, Communication and Energy Systems (SPICES),2015, 1-5.
- [3] Gormer, S., Muller, D., Hold, S., Meuter, M. and Kummert, A. Vehicle recognition and ttc estimation at night based on spotlight pairing. Proceedings of 12th international

IEEE conference on intelligent transportation systems ITSC, 2009, 1-6.

[4] Uttamkumar Dravidam and Sabri Tosunoglu, “A survey on automobile collision avoidance system”, Florida International.

[5] Kavitha, K.V.N., Bagubali, A. and Shalini, L. V2v wireless communication protocol for rear end collision avoidance on highways with stringent propagation delay. In proceedings of international conference on advances in recent technologies in communication and computing ARTCom, 2009, 661-663.

[6] Milanés, V., Pérez, J., Godoy, J. and Onieva, E. A fuzzy aid rear-end collision warning/avoidance system. Expert Systems with Applications **39** (10) (2012) 9097-9107.

[7] Bella, F. and Russo, R. A Collision Warning System for rear-end collision: a driving simulator study. Procedia-Social and Behavioral Science, 2011, 676-686.

[8] Kaempchen, N., Schiele, B. and Dietmayer, K. Situation assessment of an autonomous emergency brake for arbitrary vehicle-to-vehicle collision scenarios. IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems **10** (2009) 678-687.

